

**Proceedings of the
2019
Society of Wood Science and
Technology
International Convention**

**Convention Theme: Renewable
Materials and the Wood-based
Bioeconomy**

Edited by Susan LeVan-Green

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Purdue University, USA*

**October 20-25, 2019
Tenaya Lodge
Yosemite National Park, California, USA**

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The Forest for the Trees: Understanding the Experiences of Female PhDs in Forestry-Related Academia

Amy Simmons

InnoRenew CoE and University of Primorska, Slovenia

Abstract

In science, technology, education, and mathematics (STEM) fields men and women are pursuing undergraduate degrees in similar numbers. However there is a leaky pipeline - women comprise less than 30% of researchers. This is especially true in the forest research sector, which remains traditionally male dominated. This study focuses on the experiences of female researchers with PhDs working within forestry-related research. The traditional and perhaps even chauvinistic culture of the field contributes to its ongoing gender disparity; indeed, it was difficult to find women and non-binary doctoral candidates to interview for this study, as the field remains male dominated and somewhat unwelcoming to anyone but cisgender men.

Fifteen female, PhD-level researchers were interviewed to assess their experiences and perceptions in the framework of gender diversity at forestry-related research universities and institutes in Europe and North America. Interviewees answered questions on topics like the atmosphere and culture of their workplace; the advantages and disadvantages of being a female in research; and challenges experienced during the promotion processes. Researchers discussed many common themes, such as, diverse teams do better research and positive change is slowly occurring. However many interviewees also stated that females are often isolated or excluded from 'old boy' networks and that having a family while meeting requirements for promotion within the existing structure is challenging. The study gave us insights regarding the lack of females in forestry research, and enabled us to identify ways to increase gender equality in research and innovation.

KEYWORDS: gender gap; forestry; academia; science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM); gender diversity; gender disparity;

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